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Effects of Sleep Deprivation to the Mental Health Stability of Selected Grade 9 Students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School (RMCHS)

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Submitted To

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DEDICATIONS AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The proponents would like to dedicate this study to Father God, for giving us the opportunity and the will to fulfill the studied topic, ***Effects Of Sleep Deprivation To The Mental Health Stability Of Selected grade 9 Students Of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School (RMCHS).***

The proponents would also like to thank our research adviser for this subject matter, Mrs. Charito Amabao; along with his student teacher during the time of this study, Mr. John Mark Geneses Villarosa, for being diligent in consulting in proxy to our research adviser.

The researchers would also like to extend their gratitude towards the thirty students that answered the survey in order to complete this research. Without them, the researchers would not be able to complete the study's objectives and conclude their hypothesis.

The researchers would like to give this page to recognize Christopher Kenshin Manong, who was scheduled to go overseas and unfortunately didn't able to work for the group.

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, students have mental health issues that have been circulating all around the country. Peer pressure, tons of schoolwork, and family matters do contribute in the instability of the mind. Sleep deprivation, on the other hand, is the lack of time needed for the body to rest and heal itself from our activities. Students cannot focus or give all of their effort with the damaging mental volatility that they have and multiple happenings of sleep deprivation can also ruin our activities especially for students that endure scholastic activities. In this study, the researchers intend to seek how sleep deprivation affects the students in correlation to the mental health of students. This study will be done to the selected 9th Graders of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School. A survey questionnaire was used in order to conduct it to the selected sections (Rizal, Bonifacio, and Mabini) and the results reveal that most of the Grade 9 students do have sleep deficiency and it has a direct effect on their mood, their social skills, and their response to environmental stimuli.

Keywords: *sleep deprivation, mental health stability, RMCHS*

I. THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

The face of the education system of the Philippines changed after the shift of the ten-year curriculum to the global standard of twelve years as the PNoy Administration believes that adding more years to basic education in the Philippines could help solve the problems of unemployment, keep with global standards, and help Filipino students to have more time to choose the career that best suits their skills (Bernabosa, 2013; Capilitan *et. al.*, 2015). Six years after the implementation of the newly-adjusted program, it was now fully absorbed and taken by all of the schools in the Philippines, led by the Department of Education or DepEd. It also introduced a higher standard in education, by the introduction of the Senior High School that will also result to a shift in the achievement tests that are given by

Department of Education, namely the National Career Assessment Examination for the third year (now Grade 9) high school students and the National Achievement Test which will be taken by Grades 6, 10 (formerly known as fourth years) and 12 students.

Students that reached the new curriculum will adjust to the status of the new modules and lessons that were issued by the Department of Education. In lieu with these adaptations, DepEd also changed the structure of learning in the subjects, the example being the subjects pertaining to Social Studies and Philippine History. It also reinforced the study of dialects and mother tongues, which is good for the conservation of the native languages. The enhancement of the education system is so timely, yet it faced criticisms and issues such as the lack of funding and the adjustment of the students.

With the advancing stage of education in the country, Filipino students should still be balanced learning and enjoying. Also, students need sleep as they go through their studies, as supported by the iconic phrase “with a sound mind and a sound body”. The modern times of studying in the Philippines began to release another protuberance in the stigma, and unfortunately, this is the rising tide amongst Filipino students, which are issues relating to their sleep periods and mental instabilities. Nowadays, students have mental health issues that have been circulating all around the country. Peer pressure, tons of schoolwork, and family matters do contribute in the instability of the mind and also the lack of rest between the learners. For the new curriculum, these problems should be properly monitored not only by those inside the school, but also the people that are responsible for the students outside the four corners of a campus.

The main objective of the study will lead out to a developmental probation seeking to determine how to solve, or to help out Filipino junior high school students in focusing their sleep installments day by day without having the impasse of distress in their school works. If successful, the results may be used to provide assistance in maintaining the welfare of Filipino students in lieu with their learning,

entertainment, and relaxation that will guarantee a sound mind alongside with a healthy lifestyle for them.

The researchers hypothesize that students who are more likely to experience multiple occasions of sleep deprivation will have an inferior mental stability compared to those students who are less likely to have episodes of sleep deprivation, particularly those who have 6-8 hours of sleep. The results would be going to that way since sleep deprivation is detrimental to the cognitive functions of our brain that is a necessity to the students themselves.

As said by Lange *et. al.*, sleeping is a recurrent state of bodily rest and reduced consciousness that serves multiple functions, which is associated to the circadian system. This is exemplified by tainted perceptions, inhibition of nearly all voluntary muscles, relatively inhibited sensory activity, and reduced interactions with surroundings (Majde & Krueger, 2005). During sleep, most of the body's systems are in an anabolic state, helping to restore the immune, nervous, skeletal, and muscular systems; these are vital processes that maintain mood, memory, and cognitive function, and display an important role in the utility of both endocrine and immune systems (NINDS, last revised: 2019). The National Sleep Foundation, the time allotted for adults to sleep must be adequate to 7-9 hours, and for teenagers, in which the range of ages are significant for the study, must have 8-10 hours of sleep.

It is essential to have an adequate amount of sleep and it is varying amongst the characteristics of an individual. By resting for a couple of hours we let our bodies to revitalize, rejuvenate, and recharge itself. Between sleep periods there are two types of phases, namely, the NREM (non-rapid eye movement) phase and the REM (rapid eye movement) phase (Solms, 2000; Andreasen & Black, 2006). By definition, NREM is the phase where there are few or noted motions occurring in the eye during sleep and most of the bodily functions here are parasympathetic and is more thought-based (La Berge, 1992; Solms, 1997; Manni, 2005). REM is more hallucinatory and majority of dreams occur on this phase.

Lacking the stages of these phases may disrupt the necessary rest that our bodies need. Ferrara and De Gennaro in 2001 stated that the lack of sleep is a major issue in society today, causing many people, including students, to suffer from health problems related to sleep deprivation. Sleep deprivation, promotes unhealthy habits, daytime sleepiness, clumsiness, and an irregular change in body weight as said by Taheri *et. al.* in 2004. Although this is negative for the cognitive functions of our body, studies do show an optimistic result concerning the alertness and the mood of the individual but still never went through the consequences of prolonged episodes of sleep deprivation (Alhola & Polo-Kontola, 2007).

According to the Consumer's Version of the Merck Manual (last revised: 2017), mental health disorders, both psychiatric and psychologic, involve disturbances in thinking, emotion, and/or behavior; and nearly 50% of adults experience a mental illness at some point in their lives. In fact, 4 of the 10 leading causes of disability among people aged 5 and older are mental health disorders, with depression being the number one cause of all illnesses that cause disability.

In correspondence with an article of the Association of Children's Mental Health that came from Kessler *et. al.* in 2005, one out of five children have a diagnosable emotional, behavioral or mental health disorder and one out of ten young people have a mental health challenge that is severe enough to impair how they function at home, school or in the community. Estimates show that 80% of people with ages 6-17 do not receive the necessary mental health care that they need (Kataoka *et. al.*, 2002). Symptoms such as poor eating habits, insomnia, depression and suicidal tendencies as consequences of academic stress must be encouraged to seek help from medical health professionals (Thuraiselvam & Thang, 2015).

Since the procedures and fruits of learning are the characteristics of improvement that connotes amendment particularly for attitude and knowledge, it must be always and enjoyable experience to the eyes of the learners. The modifications of an education system must not reach a threatening level of distress to the students, but improve the quality of their capabilities in order for them to become the responsible pioneers of the future.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Studies do show that mental health issues became the major cause of the many encounters of distress in all academic institutions, with depression being the leading cause (Merck Manual: last revised 2017). In line with this, sleep deprivation is now common to the students as studies show it. Surprisingly, the deprivation of sleep amongst students gave a new impasse to the students of today in becoming alert and sensitive in their school routines (Alhola & Polo-Kontola, 2007).

In this study, the researchers intend to seek how sleep deprivation affects the students in correlation to the mental health of students. This study will be done to the selected 9th Graders of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School that belongs to the top three sections of the Basic Education Curriculum (BEC), namely 9-Rizal, 9-Bonifacio, and 9-Mabini.

III. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

The study intends to find out the effects of sleep deprivation to the academic performance of Grade 9 students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School and supporting inquiries such as the causes, impacts, and the possible solutions that the researchers would like to propose. Specifically, the study will only look upon the psychological effects of sleep deprivation of the selected 9th graders of the school's three cream sections on the BEC namely, Rizal, Bonifacio, and Mabini.

IV. METHODOLOGIES

1. Research Design

The design's approach of the given study is quantitative; since it focuses more on the ability to complete statistical analysis (Mersdorf, 2016). A survey research design was employed in this study to establish a foundation in finding

out the effects of sleep deprivation to the academic performance of Grade 9 students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School. To define it, survey research design is an extensive cross sectional approach, where a number of cases are considered at a particular time and the data is gathered to study the opinions, behavior, attitudes, habits, desires, values and beliefs etc. (Farooq, 2015).

2. Research Instrument

The only research instrument that was used is the survey questionnaires prepared by the researchers to determine the effects of sleep deprivation to the academic performance of the chosen respondents. Using surveys and questionnaires is the most common techniques used in quantitative research (Mersdorf, 2016).

3. Determining the Population Size

The chosen population is the Grade 9 students of the three cream sections of the Basic Education Curriculum (BEC) at Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School, which are the sections of 9-Rizal, 9-Bonifacio, and 9-Mabini. The proponents will be executing the sampling technique to the selected respondents in order to cut down time and resource limitations. For this study, the researchers would use the Slovin's formula for obtaining the sample size. This is for the reason that (1) the population of the selected respondents is small and (2) for the ease of sampling the respondents.

Noting n as the sample size, we will arrive at the formula, which is

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

where the size of the population is denoted as N and e being stands for the margin of error (Almeda *et. al.*, 2010).

After determining the population of the students in the sections they belong, the researchers will use the Slovin's formula in order to substitute the data we collected which will give the researchers to an approximate number of 30 respondents (see below) from the top three sections from the Basic Education Curriculum (BEC) program of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School.

$$n = \frac{126}{1+126(0.025)} = 30.36144578; \approx 30$$

4. Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers will use questionnaires as their research instrument, separated by two important parts. The first part is the demographic profile of the respondent (name, age, and section) and the second part is the set of questions that will let the researchers attain the responses that will answer the questions in the given study. The second part contains 10 questions, which tackle about the deprivation of sleep that the students experience due to academic stress and the impacts of the main dilemma to their own environment. For formality, the conducted survey is signed by the study adviser, Mrs. Charito Amabao along with his student teacher during the time of this study, Mr. John Mark Geneses Villarosa.

The survey questions used can be seen at Appendix II – Survey Questions.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

These are the following results that are gathered by the researchers on the respondents.

(results are located on the next page)

1. HOW MANY HOURS DO YOU GET ON A REGULAR SCHOOL NIGHT?

2. WHAT TIME DO YOU NEED TO WAKE UP ON A SCHOOL MORNING IN ORDER TO NOT BECOME LATE FOR CLASS?

3. WHAT TIME DO YOU GO TO BED AT NIGHT?

4. HOW MANY HOURS DO YOU SPEND IN ACTIVITIES /SPORTS AFTER A NORMAL SCHOOL DAY?

5. RESPONSE OF THE STUDENTS ON QUESTIONS 5-10

QUESTION	GIRLS		BOYS	
	YES	NO	YES	NO
5. HAVE YOU EVER FALLEN ASLEEP IN CLASS BEFORE?	15 (50%)	3 (10%)	7 (23.33%)	5 (16.67%)
6. DO YOU FEEL EXHAUSTED THROUGHOUT THE DAY?	18 (60%)	0 (0%)	5 (16.67%)	7 (23.33%)
7. DO YOU FEEL LIKE NOT GETTING ENOUGH SLEEP ON A SCHOOL NIGHT HAS AN ILL EFFECT ON YOUR DAY?	15 (50%)	3 (10%)	11 (36.67%)	1 (3.33%)
8. DOES THE LACK OF SLEEP AFFECT YOUR ABILITY TO RESPOND TO THE HAPPENINGS IN YOUR ENVIRONMENT?	16 (53.33%)	2 (6.67%)	7 (23.33%)	5 (16.67%)
9. DO YOU FEEL MORE SOCIABLE AND JOLLIER WHEN YOU GET 8 OR MORE HOURS OF SLEEP?	16 (53.33%)	2 (6.67%)	6 (20%)	6 (20%)
10. DOES THE LACK OF SLEEP AFFECT YOUR MOOD OR EMOTIONS THROUGHOUT THE DAY?	15 (50%)	3 (10%)	9 (30%)	3 (10%)

The questionnaire that was prepared by the researchers comprises of questions which will provide us the answers for our problem statement, which is to find out how sleep deprivation affects the students in correlation to the mental health of students. The results of the inquiry from the first question show that the students lack 1-3 hours of their required sleep according to the report of the National Sleep Foundation. Question #3 also supported the view of the results from Question #1, since most of the students that were interviewed sleep from 9-11 PM. Since the schedule of Grade 9 students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School is on the afternoon session, the students wake up mostly from the interval of 6-7 AM. The results of the three questions, it can be inferred that the students sleep on near midnight periods and wake up on a somewhat latish morning.

From the fourth question, it can be implied that most of the Grade 9 students lack physical activity. Defining it, physical activity are bodily movements produced by skeletal muscles that requires the expenditure of energy and produces progressive health benefits (National Institutes of Health, 1995; WHO & WHO-WPRO, 2009). This is alarming since recent studies revealed that levels of inactivity are high in virtually all developed and developing countries (WHO & WHO-WPRO, 2009). According to the website of the UK's National Healthcare Service and WHO-WPRO, children and young people should spend at least an hour of doing moderate to vigorous activities.

Questions #5 to #6 do form a pattern on the reaction of the students when they responded to it. It is shown that they experience daytime sleepiness, and throughout the day they are most likely to be exhausted due to the deficiency in their rest periods. In connection to a study by Wong *et. al.*, it is heavily entailed that the connection of sleep deprivation to the students promotes them being more agitated about academic requirements and activities and tense to the environment they are exposed to, which supports Questions #6 to #10.

V. CONCLUSION

Results show that most of the students do not get an adequate amount of sleep time since the time needed for sleep among teenage students is 8-10 hours in accordance to the report of the National Sleep Foundation. This statement is supported by the response of the students in the third question that reveals that the majority of them sleep on dead hours. Aside from that, most of them do not spend their free time for exercise activities or sports.

From the results, it shows that most of them are sleep deprived and it affects their quality of time that they use up on their schooling. The respondents also believe that the effect of sleep deprivation to them makes them more moody and may contribute to them getting a rough day in their school activities.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The generalization of this study will contribute to creating new solutions and new innovations for the government to look upon in order to cope with the rising trend of problems regarding with the new educational system that is still doing attunements (which is the K-12 system adapted six years ago).

The researchers would like to turn in recommendations for a similar study like this in order to include a qualitative assessment prior to the behaviors of the students on class. The results of the study will also assist teachers in creating new ways to approach their students that are facing the problems of sleep deprivation.

Furthermore, teachers would be able to adjust the learning styles of their students to fit the compulsory techniques that are still efficient to the learners. In addition, the findings of the study will benefit the leading head teachers and the staff because they can now study more about the issue and provide a solution in the form a seminar so they can dissipate new practices while being methodical to the mandate of teaching.

Concerning about this topic, the researchers would like to point out (for the future researchers) that the given focus of this topic can be transformed into a study which performs descriptive statistics, by the usage of sleep quality indexes such as the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index for the quality of sleep, the Epworth Sleepiness Scale for daytime sleepiness, and the Rosenberg self-esteem scale for the self-esteem and the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale for the mood; in which can be used for a more meaningful subject matter. In addition to this, the proponents suggest that a bigger sample size must be used for the future researchers that would want to choose this as a topic. This is recommended in order to have a proper inquiry on other levels in the Junior and Senior High School (Grade 7, Grade 9, Grade 10, Grade 11, and Grade 12).

Recommendations of an online research survey design will be more efficient for a bigger sample size for a research topic.

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APPENDICES

Appendix I

Derivation of the Sampling Technique

The usage of the Slovin's formula is heavily inclined by researchers and statisticians because of its convenience, but it is heavily misused as noted by Punzalan & Tejada in 2012. In order to derive the formula, we will look back to the work of Cochran in 1977 in which he presented the following formula below when working for a finite population, which is used for creating inferences on the population proportion P under simple random sampling without replacement (abbreviated as SRSWOR).

The formula given by Cochran in 1977 is

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{n_0}{N}}$$

where:

$$n_0 = \frac{z^2 p(1 - p)}{e^2}$$

N is the population size, z is the standard normal variate based on the confidence coefficient, p is the estimate for P , and e is a specified margin of error. Assuming a 95% of confidence so z is approximately equal to 2, we will end up through the Slovin's formula. In cases where P is absent to the knowledge of the researchers, the conservational approach is to maximize.

$$p(1 - p) = \frac{1}{4} - \left(\frac{1}{2} - p\right)^2$$

Noting that this quantity is maximized when the subtrahend is 0, that is, when $p = 0.5$. We then introduce $p = 0.5$ and $z = 2$ in the equation for n_0 does yield into

$$n_0 = \frac{2^2 (0.5)(1 - 0.5)}{e^2} = \frac{1}{e^2}$$

in order for the formula to become

$$n = \frac{\frac{1}{e^2}}{1 + \frac{1}{N}} = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

which is now the Slovin's formula. This implies that both Cochran's formula and Slovin's formula do coincide when estimating P using a confidence coefficient of 95% and 0.5 for the estimation of the population proportion (Punzalan & Tejada, 2012).

Appendix II

Survey Questions

(located on the next page)

Name:

Age:

Grade and Section:

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours 5-7 hours
8-12 hours 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM 4-5 AM
5-6 AM 6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM 9-11 PM
11-1 AM Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours 0-2 hours
2-4 hours 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES NO

Signature

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Appendix III

Approval for Survey

Appendix IV

Survey Results

Name: JANA B. CORRE
Age: 14
Grade and Section: 9-MABINI

F

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?
0-4 hours
8-12 hours
 5-7 hours
 13+ hours
2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?
3-4 AM
5-6 AM
 4-5 AM
 6-7 AM
3. What time do you go to bed at night?
7-9 PM
11-1 AM
 9-11 PM
 Later than 1 AM
4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?
No hours
2-4 hours
 0-2 hours
 4-6 hours
5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?
 YES
 NO
6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?
 YES
 NO
7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?
 YES
 NO
8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?
 YES
 NO
9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?
 YES
 NO
10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?
 YES
 NO

Signature

Name: Sapitan, Jeremiah ✓

Age: 16

Grade and Section: 9-B201 M

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours ~~5-7 hours~~
8-12 hours 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

~~3-4 AM~~ 4-5 AM
5-6 AM 6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

~~7-9 PM~~ 9-11 PM
11-1 AM Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours ~~0-2 hours~~
2-4 hours 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES ~~NO~~

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES ~~NO~~

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

~~YES~~ NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

~~YES~~ NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

~~YES~~ NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

~~YES~~ NO

Signature

Name: Alexander Ilustre

M

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9-Donitaub

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours
~~8-12 hours~~

5-7 hours
13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM
5-6 AM

4-5 AM
~~6-7 AM~~

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM
11-1 AM

~~9-11 PM~~
Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours
~~2-4 hours~~

0-2 hours
4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES

~~NO~~

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES

~~NO~~

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

~~YES~~

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

~~YES~~

NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

~~YES~~

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

~~YES~~

NO

Signature

Name: Justine Kate M. Copino

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9-Mabini

m

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

- 0-4 hours
- 8-12 hours
- 5-7 hours
- 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

- 3-4 AM
- 5-6 AM
- 4-5 AM
- 6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

- 7-9 PM
- 11-1 AM
- 9-11 PM
- Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

- No hours
- 2-4 hours
- 0-2 hours
- 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

- YES
- NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

- YES
- NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

- YES
- NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

- YES
- NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

- YES
- NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

- YES
- NO

Justine Kate

Signature

Name: Don Jaime Custodio

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9 - Rizal

M

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

- a ~~0-4~~ hours b 5-7 hours
c 8-12 hours d 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

- a 3-4 AM b 4-5 AM
c 5-6 AM d ~~6-7~~ AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

- a 7-9 PM b ~~9-11~~ PM
c 11-1 AM d Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

- a No hours b ~~0-2~~ hours
c 2-4 hours d 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

- ~~YES~~ NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

- ~~YES~~ NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

- ~~YES~~ NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

- YES ~~NO~~

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

- YES ~~NO~~

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

- ~~YES~~ NO

Signature

Name: Garrille Torres

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9-22A

F

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours

~~5-7 hours~~

8-12 hours

13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM

4-5 AM

5-6 AM

~~6-7 AM~~

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM

9-11 PM

~~11-1 AM~~

Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours

~~0-2 hours~~

2-4 hours

4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

~~YES~~

NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

~~YES~~

NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

~~YES~~

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES

~~NO~~

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

~~YES~~

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

~~YES~~

NO

Garrille Torres
Signature

Name: Clarence Chavez m

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9-Bonifacio

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours 5-7 hours
 8-12 hours 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM 4-5 AM
5-6 AM 6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM 9-11 PM
11-1 AM Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours 0-2 hours
2-4 hours 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES NO

CB Chavez
Signature

Name: Kayle Rose M. Santolices

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9 - mabini

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours

5-7 hours

8-12 hours

13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM

4-5 AM

5-6 AM

6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM

9-11 PM

11-1 AM

Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours

0-2 hours

2-4 hours

4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES

NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES

NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES

NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES

NO

Signature

Name: Kyle Paguad

Age: 14

F

Grade and Section:

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?
 0-4 hours 5-7 hours
 8-12 hours 13+ hours
2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?
 3-4 AM 4-5 AM
 5-6 AM 6-7 AM
3. What time do you go to bed at night?
 7-9 PM 9-11 PM
 11-1 AM Later than 1 AM
4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?
 No hours 0-2 hours
 2-4 hours 4-6 hours
5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?
 YES NO
6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?
 YES NO
7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?
 YES NO
8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?
 YES NO
9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?
 YES NO
10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?
 YES NO

Signature

Name: Karl Vincent magn

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9-Rizal

M

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours
8-12 hours

5-7 hours
13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM
5-6 AM

4-5 AM
6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM
11-1 AM

9-11 PM
Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours
2-4 hours

0-2 hours
4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES

NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES

NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES

NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES

NO

Signature

Name: Khylla Jayme

Age: 15

F

Grade and Section: 9 Mabini

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

- 0-4 hours
- 8-12 hours
- 5-7 hours
- 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

- 3-4 AM
- 5-6 AM
- 4-5 AM
- 6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

- 7-9 PM
- 11-1 AM
- 9-11 PM
- Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

- No hours
- 2-4 hours
- 0-2 hours
- 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

- YES
- NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

- YES
- NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

- YES
- NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

- YES
- NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

- YES
- NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

- YES
- NO

Jayme
Signature

Name: *Antonio Magsaysay*

M

Age: *17*

Grade and Section: *9 - Miguel*

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

- 0-4 hours
- 5-7 hours
- 8-12 hours
- 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

- 3-4 AM
- 4-5 AM
- 5-6 AM
- 6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

- 7-9 PM
- 9-11 PM
- 11-1 AM
- Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

- No hours
- 0-2 hours
- 2-4 hours
- 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

- YES
- NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

- YES
- NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

- YES
- NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

- YES
- NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

- YES
- NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

- YES
- NO

Signature

Name: Nicole Soriano

F

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9-Bonifacio

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours

5-7 hours

8-12 hours

13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM

4-5 AM

5-6 AM

6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM

9-11 PM

11-1 AM

Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours

0-2 hours

2-4 hours

4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES

NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES

NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES

NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES

NO

Signature

Name: Babula, Julianna F

Age: 14

Grade and Section: 9-Bonifacio

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night? 5-7 hours

0-4 hours

5-7 hours

8-12 hours

13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes? 6-7 AM

3-4 AM

4-5 AM

5-6 AM

6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM

9-11 PM

11-1 AM

Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours

0-2 hours

2-4 hours

4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES

NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES

NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES

NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES

NO

Julianna Babula

Signature

Name: Indus, Manel ♀- F

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9 Bonifacio

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours 5-7 hours
8-12 hours 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM 4-5 AM
5-6 AM 6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM 9-11 PM
11-1 AM Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours 0-2 hours
2-4 hours 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES NO

M. Indus

Signature

Name: John Christopher P. Artienda

Age: 15

Grade and Section: IX- Mabini

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours

5-7 hours

8-12 hours

13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM

4-5 AM

5-6 AM

6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM

9-11 PM

11-1 AM

Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours

0-2 hours

2-4 hours

4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES

NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES

NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES

NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES

NO

Signature

Name: Ugaldo, Fheona Grace P.
Age: 15 yrs old

Grade and Section: 9-Rizal

F

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

- 0-4 hours
- 8-12 hours
- 5-7 hours
- 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

- 3-4 AM
- 5-6 AM
- 4-5 AM
- 6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

- 7-9 PM
- 11-1 AM
- 9-11 PM
- Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

- No hours
- 2-4 hours
- 0-2 hours
- 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

- YES
- NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

- YES
- NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

- YES
- NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

- YES
- NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

- YES
- NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

- YES
- NO

FHEONA UGALDO
Signature

Name: *Laira Mae Obuges*

F

Age: *15*

Grade and Section: *9 - Bonifacio*

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours ~~5-7~~ hours
8-12 hours 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM 4-5 AM
5-6 AM ~~6-7~~ AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM 9-11 PM
~~11-1~~ AM Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours 0-2 hours
~~2-4~~ hours 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

~~YES~~ NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

~~YES~~ NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

~~YES~~ NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

~~YES~~ NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

~~YES~~ NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES ~~NO~~

Laira Mae

Signature

Name:

Age:

Grade and Section: 9 - Maria M

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours

5-7 hours ✓

8-12 hours

13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM

4-5 AM

5-6 AM

6-7 AM ✓

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM

9-11 PM

11-1 AM ✓

Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours

0-2 hours

2-4 hours ✓

4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES ✓

NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES ✓

NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES ✓

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES ✓

NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES

NO ✓

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES ✓

NO

Support and follow my ig account: Mercedaramillo

Signature

Name: Irvine G. Diano

M

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9-Boni

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours 5-7 hours
8-12 hours 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM 4-5 AM
5-6 AM 6-7 AM

- Not morning class, although I wake up at 8-10 AM.

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM 9-11 PM
11-1 AM Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours 0-2 hours
2-4 hours 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES NO

Signature

Name: Tugzon, Rerty P

Age: 15 yrs old

Grade and Section: _____ M

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

- 0-4 hours
- 5-7 hours
- 8-12 hours
- 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

- 3-4 AM
- 4-5 AM
- 5-6 AM
- 6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

- 7-9 PM
- 9-11 PM
- 11-1 AM
- Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

- No hours
- 0-2 hours
- 2-4 hours
- 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

- YES
- NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

- YES
- NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

- YES
- NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

- YES
- NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

- YES
- NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

- YES
- NO

Signature

Name: Angel Sweet S. Herbas a

Age: 14 yrs. old

F

Grade and Section:

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours

~~5-7 hours~~

8-12 hours

13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM

~~4-5 AM~~

5-6 AM

~~6-7 AM~~

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM

9-11 PM

~~11-1 AM~~

Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours

~~0-2 hours~~

2-4 hours

4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES

~~NO~~

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

~~YES~~

NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES

~~NO~~

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES

~~NO~~

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

~~YES~~

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

~~YES~~

NO

Signature

Name: _____

Age: _____

1/1

Grade and Section: 9 - ~~ABCD~~

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours 5-7 hours
~~8-12 hours~~ 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM 4-5 AM
5-6 AM ~~6-7 AM~~

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM ~~9-11 PM~~
11-1 AM Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours ~~0-2 hours~~
2-4 hours 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES ~~NO~~

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES ~~NO~~

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

~~YES~~ NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

~~YES~~ NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

~~YES~~ NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

~~YES~~ NO

~~Parent~~
PA Isidro

Signature

Name: Julia M. Jimbulan F

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9-Bonifacio

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours
8-12 hours

~~5-7 hours~~
13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM
5-6 AM

~~4-5 AM~~
~~6-7 AM~~

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

7-9 PM
11-1 AM ✓

9-11 PM
Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours
~~2-4 hours~~

0-2 hours
4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES

~~NO~~

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

~~YES~~

NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

~~YES~~

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

~~YES~~

NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

~~YES~~

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

~~YES~~

NO

Signature

Name: Roscree Joy M. Bateria F

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9 - mabini

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours 5-7 hours
8-12 hours 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

3-4 AM 4-5 AM
5-6 AM 6-7 AM

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7-9 PM 9-11 PM
11-1 AM Later than 1 AM

4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?

No hours 0-2 hours
2-4 hours 4-6 hours

5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES NO

Signature

Name: Navarro, Muga Danielle B.
Age: 16 years old
Grade and Section: F

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?
0-4 hours
8-12 hours
5-7 hours
13+ hours
2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?
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6-7 AM
3. What time do you go to bed at night?
7-9 PM
11-1 AM
9-11 PM
Later than 1 AM
4. How many hours do you spend in activities/sports after a normal school day?
No hours
2-4 hours
0-2 hours
4-6 hours
5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?
YES
NO
6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?
YES
NO
7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?
YES
NO
8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?
YES
NO
9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?
YES
NO
10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?
YES
NO

Signature

Name: Michaela Jehn B RICO F

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9-Mabini

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours
 8-12 hours

5-7 hours
 13+ hours

2. What time do you need to wake up on a school morning in order to not become late on classes?

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4-5 AM
 6-7 AM

3. What time do you go to bed at night?

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9-11 PM
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No hours
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0-2 hours
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5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES

NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES

NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES

NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES

NO

Signature

Name: Francherza Pedruzuela

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9-Mabini

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours

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8-12 hours

13+ hours

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5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES

NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES

NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES

NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES

NO

Signature

Name: Jehan Adarayan

Age: 15

Grade and Section: 9 - Brown 5010

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

0-4 hours
8-12 hours

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13+ hours

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5. Have you ever fallen asleep in class before?

YES

NO

6. Do you feel exhausted throughout the day?

YES

NO

7. Do you feel like not getting enough sleep on a school night has an ill effect on your day?

YES

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES

NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES

NO

Signature

Name: WALICAN, Leonard Luis D.

Age: ~~10~~ 14

Grade and Section: 9-Mabini m

Dear Student, we value your feedback. Please fill out this survey with all honesty. We appreciate your participation!

1. How many hours of sleep do you get on a regular school night?

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YES

NO

8. Does the lack of sleep affect your ability to respond to the happenings in your environment?

YES

NO

9. Do you feel more sociable and jolly when you get 8 or more hours of sleep?

YES

NO

10. Does the lack of sleep affect your mood or emotions throughout the day?

YES

NO

Walican, L. D.
Signature